

Maximizing Entropy, Function-Inverse Function and Tsallis Entropy

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In an earlier note (1), we argued that Tsallis entropy based on \ln_q acts on an inverse function \exp^{-q} to yield be^{i+a} where b and a are Lagrange multipliers. In this note, we use different arguments, namely that if the maximization process uses the form to maximize: $\sum_i p(i) \text{Function}(p(i))$ subject to the constraint: $\sum_i (a+be^i) p(i)$, this is equivalent to:

$\frac{d}{dp(i)} \{p(i)\text{Function}(p(i))\} = - \frac{d}{dp(i)} \{ (a+be^i) p(i) \}$. Integrating from $p(i)=0$ to its value $p(i)$, for the case that $p(i)\text{Function}(p(i)) \rightarrow 0$ if $p(i) \rightarrow 0$ yields: $\text{Function}(p(i)) = - (a+be^i)$.

Thus, Function and $p(i)$ are formally inverse functions. We apply this idea directly to the Tsallis entropy case. In other words, $\sum_i p(i)\text{Function}(p(i))$ is the average of $F(p(i))$ and this is compared with $\sum_i (a+be^i)p(i)$ which is the average of $a+be^i$. Maximization of entropy is equivalent to equating each weight of $p(i)$ with the weight of $p(i)$ in the constraint i.e. treating the $p(i)$ as independent.

We argue that the constraints represent the relevant single particle information needed to create equilibrium i.e. e_i in collisions, for example. $F(p(i))$ on the other hand indicates the process needed to isolate $p(i)$ so that it may be equated to the information. For example, \ln suggests a linear form of $p(i)$ multiplied by other $p(j)$ s. We argue that the Tsallis \ln_q should indicate a different kind of process, perhaps one requiring $p(i)$ to a certain power, but still interacting with other $p(j)$ s, such that in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit, $p(i)$ becomes linear and multiplied to $p(j)$.

Entropy

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, entropy is often associated with the \ln of the number of permutations:

$$\ln \left\{ \frac{N!}{\text{Product over } i n(i)!} \right\} \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } n(i) = n(e_i)$$

One maximizes this quantity, which has a physical representation, subject to the constraint $\sum_i p(i) e_i$. Using Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n)$ introduces the \ln function. One may note there is no reason to use \ln in ((1)). Its role is to convert a product into a sum so that the maximization process isolates various $n(e_i)$ so that they may be linked directly with the information e_i .

In the case of reaction balance, $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$. \ln is introduced for the same reason as in the permutation case, i.e. it breaks a product into a sum, but in this case, one has independent e_i values and associates: $\ln(p(e_i))$ with constant $*e_i$. In this case, e_i is associated with the constraint used in the maximization of $\ln \{ \text{permutations} \}$ case.

Generalization of Entropy

We consider the following expression:

$$\sum_i p(i) F(p(i)) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{subject to the constraint: } \sum_i p(i) (a+be^i) \quad ((2b))$$

((2a)) is simply the average of $F(p(i))$ and ((2b)) the average of $a+bei$. The entire process of maximization of entropy subject to constraints seems to be equivalent to the following statement:

$F(p(i)) = a+bei$ ((3)) i.e. the $p(i)$ are considered to be independent.

More formally one may write:

$$d/dp(i) \{ p(i)F(p(i)) \} = d/dp(i) \{ p(i) (a+bei) \} \quad ((4))$$

Integrating from $p(i)=0$ to its value $p(i)$ yields:

$$p(i)F(p(i)) = p(i) (a+bei) \quad ((5a)) \text{ assuming that } \lim_{p(i) \rightarrow 0} p(i)F(p(i)) = 0 \quad ((5b))$$

$$\text{Dividing by } p(i) \text{ in } ((5a)) \text{ yields: } F(p(i)) = a+bei \quad ((6))$$

Thus using entropy as an average of a function $F(p(i))$ and maximizing with respect to a constraint linear in $p(i)$ seems to guarantee ((6)) if ((5b)) holds. In other words, F and p are inverse functions.

We apply this idea to the case of Tsallis entropy.

Tsallis Entropy

Tsallis entropy follows from the observation that:

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{1}{(q-1)} \{ 1 - p^{1-q} \} = \ln(p) \quad ((7))$$

The function on the LHS of ((7)) is used as $F(p(i))$ and the Tsallis entropy becomes the average of this quantity i.e.:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ p(i) \frac{1}{(q-1)} \{ 1 - p^{1-q} \} \quad ((8))$$

In the literature (2), ((8)) is maximized with respect to the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \ p(i) (a+bei)$ to obtain the value of $p(i)$ i.e.

$$p(i) = C \{ 1 - (q-1) (a+bei) \}^{1/(q-1)} \quad ((9))$$

The result ((6)), however, guarantees that $p(i)$ is the inverse of the function $F(p(i))$ if ((5b)) holds, which it does in the Tsallis case. (Note: in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case:

$\lim_{p \rightarrow 0} p \ln p$ may be shown to equal 0 using l'Hopital's rule.)

If one decides to use the LHS of ((7)) as the function to be averaged in order to create entropy, the probability corresponding to the maximized entropy is guaranteed to be the inverse of $F(p(i))$ i.e. ((9)) such that $F(p(i)) = (a+be_i)$. One then obtains ((9)) automatically from ((8)).

Choosing the Constraints

The choice of constraints is critical as the probability depends directly on these values. We suggest one should use variables which represent the information associated with interactions which create the equilibrium, for example e_i , the energy.

Choosing $F(p(i))$

Choosing F is more complicated. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $F = \ln$ which is chosen because it breaks products of probabilities or $n(e_i)!$'s into sums. In other words, one wishes to isolate $p(i)$ so it may be associated with information i in a reaction. In the MB case, information e_i adds i.e. $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ in elastic collisions while $p(i)$ s multiply so the \ln function facilitates associating a single $p(i)$ with an e_i .

In the Tsallis case, one uses a mathematical function which in the limit of $q \rightarrow 1$ yields \ln , but this function must somehow physically represent the process needed to separate out a single $p(i)$ so that it may be essentially equated to be_i (more generally $a+be_i$). For example, \ln indicates that probabilities are multiplied and so must be separated. The function $1/(q-1) (1 - p^{1-q})$ should similarly indicate what needs to be done to a $p(i)$ so that it represents the information in an interaction i.e. be_i (or more generally $(a+be_i)$). As a first guess, it may indicate that a product of the same probability is important in the equilibrium process and that only in the limit $q \rightarrow 1$ does the probability appear to the power of 1. Furthermore $p(i)$ and $p(j)$ are intertwined as the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit shows the appearance of products $p(i)p(j)$ etc.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the notion of entropy as an average of a function $F(p(i))$ i.e. $S = \sum_i p(i) F(p(i))$. This function is maximized subject to $p(i)$ and the constraint: $\sum_i p(i) (a+be_i)$ or a constraint appropriate to the collisions/information creating the equilibrium. We argue that the maximization process is formally equivalent to: $F(p(i)) = a+be_i$, i.e. probabilities are treated as independent (if $\lim_{p \rightarrow 0} pF(p) = 0$). We apply this idea to Tsallis entropy.

We suggest that $F(p(i))$ gives an indication of what is needed to isolate $p(i)$ values so that they correspond to the information governing the equilibrium i.e. be_i (or more generally be_i+a). In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, \ln is $F(p)$ and it shows that $p(i)$ values are linear and multiplied together { so that \ln separates them}. In the Tsallis case, we suggest the same probability may appear to a power in the process creating the equilibrium. Only in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit does $p(i)$ appear linearly, but at the same time multiplied to $p(j)$ in a two body collision.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
Tsallis Entropy, Function-Inverse Function Pair and Kaniadakis Stationary Distribution
2. Plastino, A.R.; Plastino, A. Brief Review on the Connection between the Micro-Canonical Ensemble and the Sq-Canonical Probability Distribution. *Entropy* 2023, 25, 591.
[https://doi.org/ 10.3390/e25040591](https://doi.org/10.3390/e25040591)